

Exploration of Western Teacher's Style in Teaching Speaking at State Senior High School 2 Rantepao in Toraja Utara- Indonesia

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: July 05, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Western Teacher's Style, Teaching, Speaking, Model In Teaching, Students' Speaking, Students' Perception</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5070685</p>	<p><i>The objectives of this research are to describe the teaching styles that are used by Western English language teachers to teach speaking and to describe students' perception toward these teaching styles. The researcher employed a qualitative description method for the study. Data qualitative refer to interview and observation data and descriptive refer to students survey. The data resources for the research were thirty students in the first year of secondary school, aged 16-17 years old, randomly chosen, and one Western English teacher from the Netherlands. Data were collected through observation, students' surveys, and interviews. Results found five characteristics of a Western teaching style, each reflecting the role of the teacher as: (1) expert, (2) formal authority, (3) personal connection, (4) facilitator, and (5) delegator. data questioner refer to expert is 3.902% categorized moderate, formal authority is 4.594% categorized moderate, personal model is 4.289% categorized moderate, facilitator is 4.391% categorized Moderate and delegator is 4.355% categorized high. The average of the score is 4.306% categorized moderate level. Interviews indicate that the students have positive feelings toward the Western teaching styles used by this teacher in English speaking class.</i></p>

Introduction

Teaching style of English teachers can be influenced by teacher's ability, attitude, approaches, and behavior. They use all the facilities or tools in the classroom that can improve their effectiveness in teaching style.

Teaching style cannot be separated from teacher's performance in their skills and personal behavior because they can influence students' willingness to learn English subject through their teaching style. To be a good teacher, must have good personality, empathy, enthusiasm, all contributing to the teacher's performance to encourage students' motivation and their interest to learn speaking subject. Most successful teachers of disadvantages students expect to vary their instructional style and strategies. If one strategy does not succeed, another one is tired.

According to Grasha (2002:47) teaching style is categorized as following one of five patterns: teacher as expert, teacher as formal authority, teacher as personal model, teacher as facilitator, teacher as delegator, teacher as expert, and teacher as authority, Teacher can take on any these roles as appropriate in the classroom. Hoy and Lee (2002:1) define teaching style as combination of the behavior, approach, method and performance of the teacher in teaching process.

In order to improve speaking skill for students English department, and to reach the requirements of new trends in the field of teaching speaking as a foreign language (EFL), EFL teachers are regularly expected to update their pedagogical, personal, social and professional competence.

Considering to the explanation above, this study aims to investigate the model used by a western teacher in teaching speaking at State Senior High School 2 Rantepao-Indonesia to know her teaching model in teaching speaking. This study is focused on one particular spoken English teacher to examine how she worked to help EFL learners in their spoken English.

It is intended to explore what features of effective teaching are described and analyzed. Therefore the objectives of this research are to explain model of western teaching styles in teaching speaking.

Review of Literature

Every teacher who teaches in the class room should have pedagogical content knowledge; the teacher can apply in the classroom as a basic of teaching in the classroom. Teaching styles are part of ways of teachers to prepare themselves in teaching process to transfer their knowledge to students. Teachers should be good performance in teaching process to influence students' ability in teach the subjects that taught in classroom, because styles performance cannot be separated with personalities, method and skill that used by the teachers. The focus of study is exploration of western teacher's style in teaching speaking.

2.1. Definitions of Teaching Style

There are any numbers of models of teaching style. According to Conti (1989:7) teaching style is the overall traits and qualities that a teacher display in the classroom and that are consistent. According to Bdam (2002:623) teaching style is the specific behavior of the teacher in teaching and interacting with media during a lesson. Furthermore Grasha, (2002:25) argues that style is important in teaching. Identifying the elements of our styles as teachers has provided to be difficult; one reason is that traditionally the concept of style has been viewed in a pejorative manner.

2.2. A Model of Teaching Style

Grasha, (2002:47) has classified teaching styles into five types

a. An Expert teacher

Possesses knowledge and expertise students need and Strives to maintain status as an expert among students by displaying detailed knowledge and by challenging students to enhance their competence. The advantage to this style is the information, knowledge, and skills such individuals possess, but the disadvantage is that the display of knowledge can be intimidating to less experienced students. An expert teaching style requires a balance between being knowledgeable and being pedantic

b. Formal authority

Concerned with providing positive and negative feedback, and establishing learning goals, the authoritarian teacher expects students to behave correct, acceptable, and standard ways. The advantage is the focus on clear expectation and structure while a disadvantages can lead to rigid, standardized, and less flexible ways of managing students and their concerns.

c. Personal model

Those who teach by personal example and establish a prototype for how to think and behave are adhering to a personal style by showing students how to do things, and encouraging them to observe and emulate the instructor's behavior, a personal style of teacher puts an emphasis on direct observation and following a role model. However, some teachers may believe their approach is the best way, leading some students to feel inadequate if they cannot live up to such expectations and standards.

d. Facilitator

A facilitator emphasizes the personal nature of teacher-student interactions, and guides students by asking questions, exploring suggestion, suggesting alternatives, and encouraging them to develop criteria to make informed choices. The flexibility teacher's style focuses on students' needs and goals, is often time consuming and is sometimes employed when a more direct approach is needed.

e. Delegator.

Delegator concerns with developing students' capacity to function in an autonomous fashion , students work independently on project or as part of autonomous fashion, advantage is help students to perceive themselves as independent learners, disadvantage is may misread students' readiness for independent work.

2.3. Cross – Culture Understanding

Grasha's research (1996:8) noted cultural differences in learning and teaching styles and East versus West. The East is considered Asian countries where Confucian teaching has been prominent and the West is that of Europe, North and South America, and their influences. A practical explanation in conjunction with teaching would be that while the West promotes interactive behavior and the teacher is more of a facilitator with a lot of group type activities, the East is primarily teacher centered or authority based and the teacher is the center of knowledge. A student from an eastern country group-work because they feel their answers reflect on the entire group not just the individual, and They are reluctant to ask questions or make mistakes that could reflect badly on others in their group. On the other hands in western teaching styles, teachers may believe they have classroom management issues because these eastern learning style students are reluctant to participate. This creates a misunderstanding between the student and their intentions versus what the teacher perceives and interprets about their actions and lack of participation.

Webel (2010:6) outlines the differences of style between Western and Eastern in teaching and learning styles. The key elements are presented here on table 1

Table 1

Western Styles	Eastern
Teacher is the facilitator	Teacher is the authority

Individual is most important	Individual is least important
Group is least important	Group is all important
Students ask questions	Students hesitant to ask
Students are encouraged to do their own thinking	Students learn official answer without question or comment
Student express self and own ideas	Student say what she/he thinks the teacher wants to hear
Group discussion is important mode of instruction	Group discussion is difficult at best
Student assimilates concepts and applies to other situation	Restatement of concepts in learned mode only
Making mistakes is part of learning	Saving face is all important
Excuses tend to be truthful	Excuse given to save face
Student sometimes polite to teacher	Student always polite, respect of authority
Students respect colleagues	Students put down colleagues
Lecture is one of several modes used often least important	Lecture is only mode of instruction
Memorization is least important means of learning	Memorization is most important means of learning
Sometimes does not required text	Always requires a text
Can begin with any concept and in any order in the book	Systematic and sequential treatment of text
Can begin with any concept and in any order in the book	Systematic and sequential treatment of text
Often relies on outside/additional resources	Relies on textbook only
Respect copyright laws	Disregards copy right laws
Students determines own class attendance	Student always comes to class
Students develop discipline.	Students are disciplined.
Students take tests in stride.	Students are test-oriented.

Method

This style research is a qualitative and descriptive exploration of the teaching style of western English as a foreign language teacher at state senior 2 Rantepao in Toraja Utara – Indonesia.

3.1. Research participants

The participants in this research were first year students of English at public secondary school in Toraja, Indonesia. The school has 12 spoken English classes of 35-40 students at this level. One class was randomly chosen to participate in this study. There were ultimately, 30 students participants, aged 16 – 17 years old. Also participating their teacher as object of observation in teaching speaking process she comes from the Nederland. For qualitative interviews, 10 students were chosen randomly from the 30 who complete the questionnaire.

3.2. Data Collection

The researcher collected the data by using three instruments, they are; Observation, questionnaire, and interview. In observation section, the researcher observed the model of western teacher's style in teaching by using an observation check list, then a questionnaire was given to 30 students who had been taught by this teacher. Finally the researcher interviewed 10 students of 30 students after the class had finished, to know students 'perception toward teacher's style.

The procedures of collecting data in this research consist of observation, questioners, and interview. The researcher observed the Western English teacher by using observation check List to identify the Western English teacher styles. Then the researcher used questionnaires to know students' perception toward the western English teacher style. Finally, students were interviewed using a set of guiding questions and also used mix languages in "*bahasa*" and English.

In other words, the researcher made descriptive notes while observing the English teacher, along with students' activities, and general classroom conditions. The researcher also collected supplementary data such teaching materials.

3.3. Data analysis Method

The documents are analyzed by using descriptive method. To know model of teaching style, the researcher used teaching style survey, then the questionnaire that given to the students has been translated into Indonesian to help students easy to understand.

Results and Discussion

Data questionnaire

The western English teacher used all 5 of Grasha's teaching styles. It can be explained, the section is the highest that the others because in teaching process there is not intimidation and punishment in teaching and learning process, all students explored independently their opinions. in expert teaching styles the teacher used seven of eight components, with the students' perception is 3,902 % it is categorized moderate level. Formal authority, the teacher used seven of eight with the students perception is 4.594%. is categorized moderate. Personal model consist of eight of eight components with the students' perception is 4.289% it is categorized moderate level. Facilitator consist of eight of eight components with the students' perception is 4.391% is categorized moderate level. And the last is delegator consist of eight of eight of components that used by the teacher with the students' perception is 4.355%t is categorized high level. It refers Grasha's ranges.

Table 2

Day	Expert	Formal authority	Personal model	Facilitator	Delegator
I	3.837	6.075	4.245	4.512	4.425
II	3.848	3.775	4.241	4.137	4.216
III	4.025	3.933	4.838	4.525	4.462
Average	3.902 (Moderate)	4.594 (Moderate)	4.289 (Moderate)	4.391 (Moderate)	4.355 (High)

Range of Low, Moderate, and high scores for each styles follow:
(Grasia 2002:167).

Table 3

Item	Low Score	Moderate Score	High Score
Expert	1.0-3.2	3.3-4.8	4.9-7.0
Formal Authority	1.0-4.0	4.1-5.1	5.5 -7.0
Personal Model	1.0-4.3	4.1-5.7	5.8-7.0
Facilitator	1.0-3.7	3.8-5.3	5.4-7.0
Delegator	1.0-2.6	2.7-4.2	4.3-7.3

Based on the finding above, the students' perceptions toward the western English teacher styles in teaching that teaching styles that used by the western English teacher can be categorized into two levels namely: moderate level and high level. Four of five types of teaching styles are moderate category level; they are expert and formal authority, personal model, and facilitator. Delegator teaching styles, the students gave high perception. And it also provided in data interview.

Observation

The data observation that found in teaching process can be explained as follow:

Teacher as Expert

According to my observation, the teaching style that included in expert as follow, In teaching, the teacher explained the objectives of the lesson such as fact, concept and principle were the most important that students should acquire. In sharing teacher's knowledge and expertise with the students, the teacher made creative Medias in teaching and learning process for example the teacher make sentence cards that can be distributed to the students. Then the students discussed in group and delegated to the students to make finish students' exercises if they did not finished yet. In learning process the teacher managed situation in classroom therefore teaching and learning process run well. On the other hands the teacher gave contextual opinions to solve about content issues. For example the teacher gave questions in contrary situation. In teaching and learning process,

the teacher gave explanation based on western culture and the students made also sentences in Eastern culture. For example the teacher gave explanation topics about snow season then the teacher asked to the students to explain their season in Indonesia, the teacher explained about popular food in west then the students also explain their popular food in Toraja – Indonesia. It means that sharing teacher's knowledge with students was very important to the teacher to make easy for the students to understand the material that presented by the English teacher. If the students had known how to make sentences and questions as topics in learning process, the teacher had willingness toward the students to leave this course well prepared for further work in classroom. Good management in classroom is important as teacher; according to her, lecturing is a significant part of how she taught. It means that while she taught, she learned in teaching she got the positive aspect that can be applied for the next teaching, it means the teacher can get new information also from students while teaching. Therefore when she taught, the teaching process can run well. If the students did not understand or the students' had different opinion to give their opinion, she explained it for them therefore, the students did well every instruction in classroom.

Teacher as formal authority

The Western English teacher set her lesson plan and syllabus by herself, before teaching in the classroom, then she explained to the students, the teacher told the students that the criteria of standard minimum (KKM) was 70 in order to pass. The teacher has responsibility to find what the students must learn and how should they learn, therefore, the teacher make group discussion and made group competition to influence students' motivation in learning process. To make clear her course subject, the teacher gave instructions every section in teaching process to provide very clear guidelines for the students in learning process. This course has specific goals and objective that the teacher to accomplish. For example, "the students are able to make Wh-questions". On the other hands the teacher expertise the students through giving contextual opinions toward the students. Finally the teacher helped through giving time estimation in finishing the exercises to develop the students' disciplines. In learning process, the teacher never gave negative feedback when the students' performance was unsatisfied. For example the teacher gave simple topic about animal to make easy for students to explain then the students explained the topic based on own word while giving opinion, the teacher gave appreciation such as very good, good answer, giving applause. The teacher provided clear guidelines for how the teacher task completed in this course through the teacher's instruction before the students did some exercises.

Teacher as personal Model

To improve students' thinking toward the materials that presented by the teacher, she gave contextual materials about wh-questions such as "what did you do yesterday?", "why do you learn English?" in learning process the teacher helped students to solve their problem if they did not answer these exercises, she went around to each group. To make understand easily the materials for the students, the teacher presented into contextual materials also, therefore, the students have high motivation in learning English. On the other hand the teacher used her experiences to illustrate point about the materials. For example "what did Stephanie do in the classroom last week?". The teacher often explained how the students used various principle and concept through giving instruction in teaching process or group discussion and personality. To give frequent verbal for the students, the teacher asked student one by one relate to the topic about wh-questions. Therefore students and the teacher were the same perception toward the material. Between the students and the teacher were closely to each others because the teacher as a "coach" who work closely to the students to correct problem in how they think and behave through learners' asking to the teacher if they did not understand in doing exercises.

It means that, the students were encouraged to emulate the example that teacher provided. To improve students' perspective in on issues that discussed by the students, the teacher gave questions about daily activities for example "why do you came to school?, or the teacher gave word such as Jakarta, Makassar, animals then the students made questions based on the words which provided, to influence students' motivation in learning process. It means the teacher establishes students' thinking and behaves in learning process.

Teacher as facilitator

The goals of teaching process can be addressed in a variety of students learning styles. It means the teacher used many techniques in teaching process for example she The teacher guided students on the course project by asking, exploring questions, and making suggestions to influence students in learning process. In course activities the students answered every question that given by the teacher then the students finished their games and exercises in group discussion. The teacher solicited students' advices about how and what to teach in this course by giving explanation before doing the exercises. At the last section the teacher gave personal support and encouraged to do well this course through giving applause to the students after answering the exercises and the teacher gave appreciation such as 'very good, nice answer, good'.

Teacher as Delegator

In observation, the researcher found that: the teacher delegated the students to do the exercises in independent activities. In this way, the students can give their opinion without fear of correction by the English teacher, then the teacher gave core points to the students. The students also give comments toward the core points that presented by the English teacher. On the other hands, the students gave critical thinking, gave contrast comments.

The teacher guided the students in learning process in discussion process. Therefore the activities in the class encouraged students to develop their own word ideas about content issues through students answer well, students gave their opinions through exercises that given by the teacher. Then the teacher gave questions one by one to design more self-directed learning experiences. The teacher gave core point of materials then the students made questions in personality. Students were truly free to answer teacher's questions because the questions given by the teacher were contextual for the learners. In teacher's explanation, the students take care toward the teacher's explanation in classroom as a responsibility such as students.

In guiding students in course project, the teacher showed pictures then students explained them. It means the students explored their opinions in learning process. To know that the course active encouraged students and take initiative and responsibility to think critically, the teacher gave contrast questions then students gave comments. In teaching, before delegating to the students to do the exercises, the teacher gave instructions how and what the students did it. Then the students did the exercises in independently without intimidation from the teacher.

Students perceptions toward teaching styles that used by the western English teacher in teaching process

To know furthermore about the teaching style that used by the western teacher's style in teaching speaking, the researcher explains the students' perception toward western teacher's styles in classroom.

Teacher as Expert

Characterizes Grasha the expert teaching styles as demonstrating expertise and maintaining that status. The expert style teacher displays his or her knowledge

Almost all students that were interviewed gave opinions that the performance of the English teacher was good. And also she said that the performance of English teacher "*dia adalah guru yang pintar, semua siswa mengatakan bahwa penjelasan dalam mengajar dapat dipahami, dia sangat menyenangkan dalam mengajar*" ("she is clever teacher, almost students said that her explanation easy to understood by the students, she is enjoy in her teaching") Then the teacher re informed material through "*explanation*" and the other students said that she provided (*guru menyediakan materi yang nyata untuk bisa dipahami*) ("content of speaking material, she taught into real life context"). It means that the teacher gave explanations into real course topic such as wh-questions and also the students said that the English teacher reviewed course topics last week through giving questions and giving some exercises. Then the perspective of the students toward how the teacher teaches, several students said that the teacher taught through medias and the other students said (*dia sangat menyenangkan did lama mengajar dan mengajar secara kreatif dan inovasi dan mengajarkan materi yang nyata*) ("she is enjoyable in teaching", she taught creatively and innovation and, teaching based on real life topics.") In teaching process all most all the students said that, the teacher used media such as book but it can be compared the other materials such as materials that searched on internet by the English teacher. Finally the students noted that the teacher created enjoyable an atmosphere in classroom through some games and quiz in learning process and the other opinion said that (*dia menyusun materi bahan ajar dengan kreatif*) ("she created material design for teaching creatively) the students really enjoy in her teaching process.

Teacher as Formal Authority

Almost all students told the researcher that there was no excuse for the students to cheat. The student told to me that "work together in learning process will be good but in testing process is not excuses " it means that the teacher gave opportunity for the students to work together in class but in testing it was forbidden work together. Another student told to the researcher that "*Ibu Stephanie tidak suka melihat siswa menyontek disaat ujian, jika ada siswa yang menyontek dia dia memberikan hukuman kepada siswa tersebut*" ("Mrs. Stephanie does not like, looked the students cheat on exam, if there were students cheat on exam, she gave punishment for them.) "Therefore it can be explained that the English teacher was strict in giving test. Then the teacher gave discipline in learning process such as, the teacher gave warning for the naughty students, and they are not discipline in learning process, she gave time for relax in learning and teaching process in the classroom.

Teacher as Personal Model

Almost all students said that, the English teacher used LCD, laptop, and the other activities "*dia adalah guru yang aktif dan lucu, dia memberikan motivasi dengan memberikan pertanyaan yang berhubungan dengan kegiatan sehari hari*" ("she was active, and funny teacher, she gave motivation by using questions related to daily activities" the teacher used creative media that encouraged students' motivation in learning process. In

guiding in teaching and learning process, the teacher used some games and quiz “ Mrs Stephanie motivated students in the classroom, and gave funny story in giving motivation toward students in learning process. therefore, the students really enjoy the teacher when she guided the students to learn English, in the made group discussion the teacher made based on “ where students’ sit or based on attendance list of students then the teacher gave quiz and games in group discussion, it means that, the teacher made simple group discussion and enjoyable. Finally according to several students, they agree toward making mistake in learning process because making mistakes is learning process every human being make mistakes therefore the students were not afraid in making mistakes in learning process. the students agree and they think that making mistakes is fair as a human being, therefore the students never be afraid in making mistakes because the English teacher never give punishment for the students who made mistake in learning process.

The English teacher gave chance how to be serious and be relaxed in learning process. Ibu Stephanie gave test in written and oral test. Finally in giving interactions, the teacher gave some games and quiz and the other students said that, the teacher “*gurunya menggunakan bahasa Indonesia untuk mempermudah pemahaman kepada kami dalam menjelaskan PowerPoint di dalam mengajar*” (“used bahasa to make easy for the students to get the point in her explanation in teaching “)it means, the English teacher used various method in giving instructional to make clear what the students to do in learning process.

Teacher as Facilitator

Almost all the students said that, the teacher helped students in their difficulties through explanation, ‘and she came to students’ sit for giving explanation in group and individually toward the students ’ that the teacher really cared for the students who has difficulties in learning process, she gave explanation in group and I privately. It is interesting for the students at the first meeting, the teacher made group discussion, then the second and the third meeting the teacher taught in direct teaching. It is not explained clearly the student’ perception toward how the teacher made group discussion. Finally the students perception toward the teacher improve students’ self-confident as follow: the students said that “ *dia memberikan beberapa permainan dengan menggunakan beberapa metode dan memberikan dorongan belajar kepada siswa, sehingga siswa tidak merasa malu untuk berbicara*” (“she gave some games by using methods and also she supported students therefore the students were not shy to speak, and she was close with the students”) the English teacher used various techniques to improve students’ self-confidence.

Teacher as Delegator

Developing students’ capacity to function in an autonomous fashion, students work independently on project. According to the students that, the delegator that used by the western English teacher in her teaching styles that “ *siswa dapat berdiskusi dan bisa memberikan pendapat mereka secara perorangan dan kelompok*” (“they could discuss, the students also could give their opinion in personality or in group discussion”) the English teacher answered the questions of the students into various techniques and enjoyable for the students therefore the students never be afraid to asked course topic that they did not yet. Then the students encouraged their own thinking through games and almost students said that the English teacher encouraged students’ thinking through games and also the students gave opinion “ *dia memberikan dorongan, dia sangat menyenangkan didalam mengajar dia memberikan tugas berdasarkan kegiatan sehari hari*” (“ she supported the students, she was enjoyable in teaching, she gave homework to write some sentences in English that related to daily activity “) the teacher encouraged students’ self-confident, she used by using simple questions, made simple statement in English. Therefore the students really enjoy it. Then the students encouraged in thinking toward English subject through students’ imagination that related toward materials in learning process and also she gave questions that it guided into a topic the English teacher gave course topics that can influence students’ critical thinking such as gave kontras topics toward the students therefore, the students encouraged their thinking. Then the students respected toward the English teacher such as “ *guru mereka sebagai orang tua mereka dan harus memperhatikan penjelasan dari dia*” (“ their parents and pay attention toward teacher’s explanation”) therefore the teaching and learning process was run well. Finally the students’ gave perception how to respect toward his/her students in learning process several students’ gave opinion that “*mereka berkompetisi didalam kelas tetapi mereka saling menolong untuk bisa belajar bersama*” (“ they have competition in classroom but they help to each others in learning process, the more we get together”) the students really respected toward his/her friend in teaching and learning process, therefore, the students enjoy the group discussion and enjoy the course topics that presented by the English teacher.

Conclusion

From the discussion of findings above, some conclusions can be explained. The conclusions cover two points as follow:

1. There are five Teaching styles that used by the western English teacher in teaching at English Department students of Toraja Christian University of Indonesia they are:

First, is expert teaching style which consists of some points namely: the teacher used fact concepts, and principle things that students should acquire, sharing teaching knowledge and expertise with students, good course preparation, how the teacher teach well, expertise in content contextual issues in teaching, teacher as a “storehouse of knowledge for the students and manage time in teaching and learning process.

Second, is formal authority Which consists of some points namely: the teacher set high standards for the students in her classroom, the teacher got positive feedback in her performance, guide well students in learning process, good responsibility what the students learn in classroom, clearly guidelines in giving tasks, made specific goals that teacher accomplished, accommodated student needs in learning process. And the teacher helped to develop students’ discipline.

Third, is Personal model, which consist of what the teacher say and do models appropriate ways for students to think about issues in the content topic, students had willingness to emulate teacher provides in learning process, the teacher stimulated students’ thinking, the teacher used her personal experiences to illustrate point about the materials, the teacher showed her performance how the students used various principle and concept in learning process. Students received frequent verbal accomplish, the students begun to think like the teacher about the course content, and the students described teacher as a “coach” who work closely with someone to correct problem in how they think and behave.

Fourth, is Facilitator, which consists of the teacher accumulated a variety of students learning styles, the teacher spend time consulting with the students, made small group discussion to improve students’ think critically, the teacher guided students on course projects by asking questions, exploring opinions and suggestion, encouraged students to take initiative and responsibility for students’ learning. Students were given free acidities in learning process and gave free activities to encourage to do well their course.

Fifth, is delegator which consists of students typically work on course projects alone with little supervision from the teacher, activities in the class encourage students to develop their own ideas about content issues, students design or more self-directed learning experiences, students think independently, students took responsibility for teaching in the classroom, students set their own pace for completing independent and group project, teacher’s approaches toward students in learning process, and teacher gave roles based on students needs.

2. The students’ perception toward teaching style that used by the western English teacher in teaching speaking is positive feeling, almost students like her model in teaching, therefore the performance of the western teacher style in teaching is category success. It falls into moderate level and high level perceptions category.

Students’ perception of themselves as learners are; students gave good appreciation toward teacher as facilitator in classroom, the teacher encourage students’ thinking by using classroom discussion, games, and questions, students can give opinion independently, teacher is good in guidance students’ activities, giving independent study, educate students to get better students’ behavior, good performance, teacher as couch in learning process, students never be afraid ask questions in classroom, the teacher is smart, good teaching, strict authority, good strategy in improving students’ self-confident such as competition in small group.

Therefore the exploration of western teacher’s styles above will be used by the researcher to make as a model in teaching at English department students at Toraja Christian University of Indonesia, and it can be used by the other researchers for the futures in teaching speaking or the other subjects. There some points as teachers should pay attention in teaching and learning process, the teacher should be a good performance, creative in teaching, make situation as students centered approaches, design creative material, interesting test, independent activities, contextual course topics, teaching real course topics, using various techniques, friendly in teaching, using some medias in teaching, monitoring teaching, guiding in teaching, encourage students’ critical thinking by using group discussion

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